

TIC'S, PUBLIC POLICIES AND REGULATIONS FOR GENDER EQUALITY IN ECUADOR

LAS TIC'S, POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS Y REGULACIONES PARA LA IGUALDAD DE GÉNERO EN ECUADOR

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RESUMEN

Esta investigación tiene como objetivo general analizar las nuevas tecnologías, las políticas públicas y regulaciones para la igualdad de género en Ecuador. Se utilizó una metodología cualitativa de diseño de investigación longitudinal de la investigación no experimental. A su vez, esta investigación tiene un alcance descriptivo y se utilizó el método analítico sintético. Se concluyó que si bien existen novedosas políticas regulatorias en torno a estos conceptos, ninguna está enfocada al uso de medios electrónicos para lograr la promoción de la igualdad de género en las redes sociales y otros instrumentos tecnológicos, cuestión que no se maneja en la actualidad.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Igualdad de Género, Tecnologías, Normas, Políticas Públicas.

ABSTRACT

This research has the general objective of analyzing new technologies, public policies and regulations for gender equality in Ecuador. A qualitative methodology of longitudinal research design of non-experimental research was used. In turn, this research has a descriptive scope and the synthetic analytical method was used. It was concluded that although there are novel regulatory policies around these concepts, none is focused on the use of electronic means to achieve the promotion of gender equality in social networks and other technological instruments, an issue that is not currently handled.

KEYWORDS: Gender Equality, Technologies, Norms, Public Policies.

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INTRODUCTION

In Ecuador the Ecuadorian constitutional norm refers to gender equality in its article 70, stating the obligation of the State to formulate and execute policies to achieve equality between men and women and to incorporate the gender approach in all plans and programs of government as well as provide the assistance required for its application. Thus, in our opinion, a model is presented that serves, as it has effectively served, as a basis for the normative development of Ecuador in this matter, since upon constitutionally establishing gender equality, Ecuador began to enforce the provisions of the norm supreme.

This process has not been easy in that country due, among other things, to the fact that as the doctrine indicates; we are in the presence of a society that, although it has made tangible progress in this regard, continues to maintain highly framed machismo margins. According to Guzñay (2018) this occurs “despite the openings and visible access of women in the political field and public spaces, not only gender violence and femicide persist among many other manifestations that develop in this sense” (p. 386).

For this reason, when talking about the current reality in Ecuador, Carvallo (2015) refers to what he calls “social transformation”, which even today continues to be part of important cultural meanings, which is why representation for vulnerable groups (like women) is more necessary than ever precisely because according to León (2015) “it becomes necessary to gain space in a society that has strong differentiating features” (p. 235). As León (2015) indicates, “the idea is to create a fairer and more egalitarian society without for that reason having to sacrifice the difference, on the contrary, the difference must be promoted” (p. 132) and that is why, at this time, it is necessary to analyze the legislative initiatives of Ecuador in this line of gender.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The problem of this research revolves around analyzing new technologies and public policies and regulations for gender equality in Ecuador.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE QUESTION

How the new technologies and public policies impact to gender equality in Ecuador?

QUESTIONS THAT SUPPORT SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

What are the new technologies for gender equality in Ecuador?

What are the public policies for gender equality in Ecuador?

What are the current legal regulations for gender equality in Ecuador?

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Analyze how new technologies and public policies impact gender equality in Ecuador

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

Determine what are the new technologies for gender equality in Ecuador.

Describe public policies for gender equality in Ecuador.

Specify the current legal regulations regarding gender equality in Ecuador.

LITERATURE REVIEW

PLANS ON EQUALITY AS NORMATIVE POLICIES REGARDING GENDER IN ECUADOR

In the first place, the Equal Opportunities Plan for Ecuadorian Women (PIO) declared as State Policy by Executive Decree 1207-A of March 9, 2006, and whose extension is from 2005-2009, was commissioned to constitute itself as a series of actions that allowed progress in the true fulfillment of women's rights and was consolidated as a search to eradicate discrimination based on gender in Ecuador. This State policy had a specific agenda that sought to comply with all the axes of planning. This agenda contained concrete actions in all matters of the plan. At that time, the aim was to incorporate the gender perspective in all areas of social interest in the country, to transform the Ecuadorian State into a more egalitarian one in areas such as education,

For its part, the National Plan for the Eradication of Intrafamily and Gender Violence, towards Children, Adolescents and Women, was also implemented from September 10, 2007, when studying its strategic axes, refers to the need to transform sociocultural patterns, the comprehensive protection system, the registration system, access to justice, and institutionalism. Specifically, the plan in question is interesting in the perspective that it offers to some realities of women, pointing out that, as different types of violence affect the daily life of the female population; this also affects their possibilities of developing in conditions of equality regarding men due to the often-irreparable consequences of these acts.

In communion with the previous paragraph, the Ecuadorian government with the participation of numerous international organizations of the United Nations and through the Decentralized National Participatory Planning System (SENPLADES) designs the well-known "Atlas of Inequalities" which is a situational analysis of Ecuador in this matter. There, mention was made of the profound inequalities that may arise in all social spheres and those that are of most important attention. It is a study by regions that clearly showed the need to

establish deeper policies in all government spheres and communion with the constitutional precepts of the moment, but of which we can say that although it analyzes inequalities in education, labor, economic and other, Ecuador does not deal very specifically with gender equality and only analyzes this reality focused on gender violence which is, as we know, only one aspect where women are disadvantaged compared to men.

For its part in the matter of gender equality, the participation of Ecuador in conjunction with international organizations is also of interest. Thus, by being part of "UN WOMEN" since its creation in 2010, measures such as the "United Nations Framework for Cooperation in Ecuador" are implemented, a government initiative that would run until 2018 from 2015. It was established within the executive summary of said State policy that non-discrimination, gender equality, and the eradication of violence were part of the margins of cooperation.

In turn, gender equality was included as the expected result number 3. The aim was to "promote gender equality through its inclusion in national and local public policy instruments, and specifically in territorial development plans" (Source, date, p.?). To achieve this, it is proposed to reinforce some key aspects in this regard, especially at the budgetary level, which will make it possible to provide the necessary resources to the institutions to achieve gender equality. It is also intended to strengthen institutional capacities within the State, to include a gender approach as indicated in the executive summary.

The framework contained different expected results, including number 2 of the "Reduction of inequity gaps for cohesion, inclusion, and quality of life", according to which, in the form of cooperation, the United Nations would support the Ecuadorian State to strengthen all its capacities to provide social protection services and among them, priority attention groups should be considered, which includes women and girls. It also needs to be said that within the final report of the framework's auction results and specifically in "Results Group 3" it is pointed out that by 2018, institutional capacities have been strengthened to promote gender equality and the eradication of forms of discrimination.

We see then how this Cooperation Framework has allowed Ecuador not only to work together with an international organization as important as the UN WOMEN but also to apply policies that are truly effective in improving the conditions of inequality due to gender motive that is lived in society. We believe that this is a positive initiative, which also opens the basis for the development of actions that allow women to be incorporated into all spheres of the practical life of that State.

On the other hand, on September 22, 2017 the National Development Plan was created where government parameters to be followed until 2021 are established. In the specific case of equality, it is established that from the

gender perspective and in Ecuador, women have achieved greater access to education at all levels of education, but this has also generated other problems that persist, such as segregation by type of career and other limitations that do not allow their empowerment. Therefore, said State policy concludes with the need to implement actions that allow the progressive disappearance of gender gaps in all social senses.

However, Ecuador also highlights its considerable normative development regarding gender equality. In this way, in the first approximation, the Organic Law of the Council for Citizen Participation and Social Control of September 22, 2009, last modification of November 24, 2014, which within the principles that correspond to its actions, points to equality and focus of the genre. The norm establishes that said equality will be guaranteed to all citizens and in all public and social life of the State according to its article number 2. The latter must be combined with another contention provision in its article 19 that establishes that parity must be guaranteed alternated between men and women.

GOVERNMENT POLICIES OF ECUADOR IN THE FORM OF LEGAL STANDARDS TO PROMOTE GENDER EQUALITY IN ECUADOR: SPECIAL MENTION TO THE NATIONAL COUNCILS FOR EQUALITY

Another important aspect to mention is that one of the most important initiatives in this matter of gender equality that is born in Ecuador with these government policies necessarily part of the National Councils for Gender Equality which are a government entity created by the article 6 of the Organic Law of National Equality Councils. These Councils implemented in 2015 the “methodological tools to mainstream the principle of gender equality and non-discrimination in public investment projects”, a series of recommendations that emanate intending to focus on gender issues in all sectors of the Ecuadorian State.

The latter is a novel initiative, but it has not been the only one emanating from these bodies. The tips have carried out numerous tasks of information and communication of gender policies that have brought this problem to the university environment to create awareness in Ecuadorian society about the situation of women due to their gender condition. As the National Councils for Gender Equality themselves point out, these are small actions that seek broader strategic objectives and that only demonstrate the commitment that Ecuadorian institutions have to the attention of these policies.

We believe that, from our point of view, the fact of having created this governmental entity that specifically studies and carries out actions to contribute to gender equality has been key in the development of policies that had already been framed in the Constitution and highlighted in the government plans on our study subject. That is why, in this line of ideas, the Ecuadorian State also implements the National Agenda for Women and Gender Equality 2012-2017

that it was a binding instrument for compliance with gender equality and the prohibition of discrimination in the State. Thanks to the Agenda, it also contributes to fulfilling the constitutional mandates that we have studied on our subject of analysis through its axes of application.

However, this regulatory initiative, which governed this matter until 2017, is currently undergoing a construction process and today we can talk about the new National Agenda for the Equality of Women and LGBTI People 2017-2021, which is an institutionalized process, carried out by the National Council for gender equality where spaces for dialogue were created within the main cities of the country.

This new agenda extends its areas of application of the principle of equality to all vulnerable spheres of society. It also contemplates many more axes of action by the Ecuadorian State about gender policies. And it is a highly inclusive approach that will have the support of the United Nations Councils for Gender Equality, which reinforces the action framework for the fulfillment of all the axes to follow, among which it highlights that the gender perspective must be incorporated in every policy that is assumed thereafter.

NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND GENDER EQUALITY

Five decades of research on science, technology and gender have resulted in a greater awareness of how gender preconceptions constitute them and great advances in the incorporation of women into the science and technology professions. Gonzalez and Fernandez (2016).

Now, once the normative provisions regarding gender equality in Ecuador have been analyzed, it is extremely important to mention the issue of the digital inclusion of women that has revolutionized the modern world and that must necessarily go hand in hand with the law. So as established by Acosta-Velazquez and Pedraza-Amador (2020) "the development of new Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (...) has a strong impact on today's society based on the increasing flow of information and its management in different areas" (p. 1). For women, this generates two scenarios: firstly, their possibilities of hiring decrease if they are not sufficiently prepared in knowledge for technological changes and secondly, the female projection or those. People, in particular through social networks, can negatively affect the acquisition of that job.

Precisely with the ease with which new technologies have gained strength in our daily lives, it is also easy to have access to different sources of information that directly affect the issues that we are commenting on, which is why the approaches of these authors seem to us to be very powerful.

Another investigation that is gaining momentum at this time is that of the authors Dominguez, Lopez, and Portela (2020) who carried out a study on

violence through ICTs and it seems interesting at this moment. In the study, doctrines Dominguez *et al.* (2020) point out that “the impact that gender stereotypes have on violence through information and communication technologies (ICT) is a frequent concern in the school setting, family and individual” (p.1). So, from our perspective we are in the presence of an instrument that can be used both for the benefit of women and to harm them.

METHODOLOGY

For this research, as proposed by Gomez, Alvarez, Romero, Castro, Vega, Comas, and Velazquez (2017), a qualitative methodology was required with a research design longitudinal design appropriate to non-experimental research. In turn, such research as indicated by Gomez *et al.* (2017) has a descriptive scope and the synthetic analytical method was used to decompose the study object into parts.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it can be seen through all the regulations studied that in Ecuador the legal world has been developed by the gender perspective in two aspects: firstly, from the normative aspect, you can see the number of public policies that have been implemented to promote measures in favor of gender equality; that is, combined with other initiatives such as the creation of national councils for equality. However, from all the measures analyzed, it can be seen that aspects related to the digital age are not considered in public policies. There is no public policy in Ecuador that involves new technologies to promote gender equality. Issues that, in our modern world, can be focused on the benefit of women to achieve.

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